

ROLE OF TEACHING BIOLOGY IN HUMAN LIFE

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A teacher of Biology

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Annotation: The article covers significant points of teaching biology and its importance in human life. In addition to this the author mentioned examples of different interactive methods that can be used biology teaching process.

Key words: *contagious diseases, implementation, cognitive interest, pedagogy, philosophy, Biology-enhanced program, experimental, problem-based active.*

The progress of human civilisation has, to a great extent, been moulded along the lines of development of the biological science. Man is a social creature. People live in towns and cities. This has created several health problems such as supply of pure water, disposal of sewage and prevention of contagious diseases, so that they may not break out in epidemic form. These problems are best solved by biology. Nowadays, it is necessary to create conditions for the pupil to be able to choose a future career through a variety of activity including the ability to self-assess. One of the actual issues of present day is the formation of competitive individuality that contributes to the improvement of life. In this connection, each teacher has the following requirements for the pupil and should influence on its implementation . These requirements include: activity action, social responsibility, broad range of thinking, literacy and priority of interest towards cognitive activity. The above mentioned personal abilities are not developed themselves, but requires pedagogical conditions. The cognitive activity of each individual is the process of continuation. That's why, the education of pupils at school is the basis for developing future self-education and self-education of

himself[1]. Finding the effective ways to prepare the pupils for continuous education is one of the actual problems.

The awareness of the pupil's cognitive interest in every subject in the classroom creates such qualities as active search and research. By stimulating pupils' interest in the subject, we would increase their active creative abilities. The main task of the teacher is to educate the children to work with their cognitive activity. The core of cognitive interest is a process of thinking. The following types of work can be used to increase pupils' intellectual thinking and interest. Tasks in the form of game for the development of logical thinking. Tasks in the direction of investigation for free delivery of his opinion. Types of work aimed at transformation of given tasks. It is important to develop pupils' self-esteem, to increase their activity, to solve theoretical and educational problems in the subject, to use resourceful and cognitive games in organizing scientific research. The use of game methods in the process of the lesson will allow the pupils to further improve their knowledge, deepen their understanding and increase their thinking abilities. Educational-cognitive activity is an integral part of pedagogical process. The educational-cognitive activity includes the most important part of social phenomenon of the pupil in the pedagogical process: philosophy, sociology, psychology, pedagogy, philosophy of education, pedagogical psychology, etc. Organizing educational-cognitive activities of the pupils with sciences, knowledge systems, business skills, mental, physical, psychological processes researches the development of mind, memory, abilities, interpretation of concrete actions of implementing the action, the worldview and personal development ways, ways of formation. The cognitive action is important for the general development of the pupil and formation of individuality. All the tendencies of the action under the influence of cognitive actions are developed[2].

Cognition requires not just the intensity of thinking, also the activeness of major tendencies of the action. For mastering the knowledge, work should be

done, such as keeping, sequencing, clarifying, analyzing and generalizing. It can be considered as one of the main types of activity of the pupil, such as labor. Because, first of all, cognition is a world-wide tendency that represents the world of society. Secondly, the person knows definite thing and phenomenon through the cognitive action without opening the novelty. Informative activity is the special phenomenon of the pupil's enthusiasm and diligence to study and know. In order to understand the new material of the teacher, the pupil needs to listen to him to extend his knowledge and to do the works as experiment. Because, it is impossible to be aware of the progress of given material in repeating consciously, in learning new knowledge and skills. That is to say, the activity of the pupil should be at all stages of the learning process. When cognitive activity of the pupil is developed during the lesson, the following elements of mental abilities will be developed: intelligence, observation, thinking and speech independence. Many works of poets, teachers and methodologists have been devoted to the development and formation of cognitive activity of pupils.

Biology-enhanced program requires each teacher to develop and enter the flexibility and skills of pupils through the provision of unity of education and upbringing, mastering the methodology of developmental learning, the implementation of interdisciplinary communication and teaching process optimization. Accordingly, at the lesson, we should bring the pupils to develop deeper, more accurate knowledge, skills and creative abilities. In order to stimulate pupils' interest in the lesson, we need to properly select the form and method of teaching[3]. The lesson would be very interesting and attractive with the use of pedagogical technologies in teaching biology. The lessons learned through innovative technology have been demonstrated in practice were an exciting, attractive and related to modern requirement. In the control experiment, we observed that during the observation period, pupils were concentrated on the topic, understood and discussed. As a result, we have seen that there is a lack of

new information, interactive teaching methods and pedagogical-psychological training that increase the pupils' interest in biological education. Therefore, we have chosen the technologies and techniques that can be used at the lesson with the participation of pupils. At the biology lesson it is effective to use Zh. Karaev and Zh. Kobdikov's teaching methods called 'Three-dimensional methodical system' in the formation of cognitive activity of the pupils (intuition, perception, memory, thinking, conclusion, imagination, attention, skills) . Nowadays, it is necessary to create conditions for the pupil to be able to choose the future specialty through the possibility of observing himself in different activities.

We have been organizing cognitive and interesting biological games such as adventures, anagrams, inwords, loto and various tasks and logic thinking, memory, mind and etc. to improve and develop pupils' cognitive activity and interest in biology lessons. The association method or the «Mind map» — the mind (thinking) map and if the illustration pictures have a lot of pictures in the tasks, more cognitive interest of the child will be increased. For example, a biological loto game can be created and used in all classes. In the 9th grades, in order to develop their qualities such as logical thinking, mind, memory and others, cognitive games such as anagrams, in words, loto games have been organized. The aim of the pedagogical experiment is to increase pupils' cognitive activity and interest in studying biology lessons, in particular the chapter «Nervous system»[4]. In the second part of our lesson, pupils were divided into five groups, explaining the purpose of each group, tasks were given in order to compare biological dictation, filling charts, essay writing, supporting drawings and venn diagrams.

To sum up all given facts above, it should be noted that in biology education, selected teaching methods should support learning biology, learning to do biological science and learning about biological science. Several biological topics require approaches promoting experimental problem-solving and process-

based skills. The focus is on science investigation processes and the goal is to reach valuable learning results, and students therefore need crucial science content knowledge as well as autonomous learning. This, however, seems to create difficulties for the so-called working memory, which again impairs the self-regulation competencies. Therefore it is important to implement teaching methods including both autonomous learning and instructional activities, and to vary the level of openness of experimental tasks. The implementation of problem-based active learning models have positive effects on students' academic achievements and their attitudes to science courses, while implementation of problem-based learning and group investigation encourages students to think critically through planning, arguing, stating questions and problems, and providing solutions to environmental problems. Biological field-based activities, e.g., fieldwork and field trips, provide students with authentic and interactive experiences and experiential learning opportunities, which increase students' interest and enhance their learning. Students' engagement in field-based activities plays an essential role in learning biological issues. Fieldwork provides students with a chance to observe nature and the environment and to use scientific inquiry to test ideas and concepts they have learned in the classroom. According to Hart and Nolan, fieldwork had a positive effect on students' knowledge, attitude and behavior, crucial factors also in promoting sustainability.

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